

Hirota's direct approach to multi-periodic wave solutions of the 2x2 matrix KdV equation

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Abstract

This work demonstrates how multi-periodic wave solutions of the 2x2 matrix KdV equation can be constructed using multidimensional theta functions. Hirota's direct approach to nonlinear evolution equations is applied to commuting matrices.

Keywords: Soliton-like equations; Equations involving linear operators, with operator unknowns; Multidimensional Theta functions; Hirota's direct approach.

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1 Introduction

Let U and V denote linear operators, and $U + V$ and UV are the sum and product, respectively. We call

$$V_t + 3V_x V_x + V_{xxx} = C \tag{1.1}$$

the *operator valued Hirota-KdV equation* with unknown operator V and given constant operator C . Clearly, $U = V_x$ solves the *operator valued KdV-equation* $U_t + 3UU_x + 3U_x U + U_{xxx} = 0$. The classical work on operator valued soliton-like equations is [9]. In his book Marčenko constructs solutions using

logarithmic derivatives of operator valued functions: $V = 2F^{-1}F_x$. However, the solutions he found are non-periodically. For further reading please see Bauhardt and Pöppe [2] and Schiebold[10].

Hence we can pose the question whether it is possible to construct matrix periodic wave solutions using logarithmic derivatives of matrix valued functions. The short paper [1] demonstrates that a particular 2×2 matrix KdV elliptic soliton - the cnoidal wave solution - turns out to be a logarithmic derivative of a 2×2 -matrix, whereby the matrix elements are Neville theta functions. The aim of this paper is to generalize that formula on g -dimensional theta functions. We will restrict ourselves to 2×2 -matrices of the form $F = f \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + h \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. Because matrices of this kind commute with each other, Hirota's bilinear method ([5, 6]) continues to function. We will show that our ansatz $V = 2F^{-1}F_x$ is a solution of the operator valued transformed KdV equation if the theta constants of certain 2^g theta functions of the dimension g fulfill particular linear differential conditions. As in the scalar case, see Hirota and Ito [6], we use the addition formula of g -dimensional theta functions for matrix case too.

The last section deals with some numerical experiments: In the case of $g = 2$, we numerically solve the differential conditions mentioned above and plot the corresponding solutions of the 2×2 matrix KdV equation. Admittedly, the values of the input parameters for these experiments are rather random. It was about specifying some solutions of the matrix KdV equation.

The calculations were performed with the SAGEMATH library *Abelfunctions* by C. Swierczewski et al.,cf. [11, 12], which implements the multidimensional theta function.

In contrast Treibich [13] constructs conditions on a compact Riemann Surface to give rise to matrix KdV elliptic solitons.

2 Ansatz

Throughout the paper we will follow the theta function notation used in [4, <http://dlmf.nist.gov/21>]. Therefore the function

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^g} e^{2\pi i(\frac{1}{2}[n+\alpha] \cdot \Omega \cdot [n+\alpha] + [n+\alpha] \cdot [z+\beta])} \quad z \in \mathbb{C}^g \quad (2.1)$$

is referred to as a g -dimensional theta function with characteristics $\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix}$. Here α, β denote g -dimensional real vectors and Ω a $g \times g$ complex, symmetric matrix with $\Im \Omega$ strictly positive definite. The g -dimensional theta function is defined by $\theta(z|\Omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega)$. On the other hand, any theta function with characteristics can be represented as a translation of $\theta(z|\Omega)$ multiplied by an exponential factor:

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) = e^{2\pi i(\frac{1}{2}\alpha \cdot \Omega \cdot \alpha + \alpha \cdot [z + \beta])} \theta(z + \Omega \alpha + \beta|\Omega), \quad (2.2)$$

see [4, <https://dlmf.nist.gov/21.2.E6>].

For thorough treatments on multidimensional theta functions we refer readers to Krazer [8] and [7]. For the convenience of the reader, we repeat in the appendix the relevant material for this work on multidimensional theta functions without proof.

We take the following ansatz:

$$F(z|\Omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.3)$$

Here ϵ is a nonzero g -dimensional vector whose entries are either 0 or 1.

To apply Hirota's method below, we have to compute the product $F(z)F(w)$ and F^{-1} .

Proposition 1. *If one of the two conditions*

- (i) $\alpha \cdot \epsilon \pmod{1} = 1/2$
- (ii) $\alpha \cdot \epsilon \pmod{1} = 0$

is true, then

$$\begin{aligned} & F(z|\Omega)F(w|\Omega) \\ &= 2 \sum_{\substack{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g \\ \epsilon \nu \text{ even (i) or} \\ \epsilon \nu \text{ odd (ii)}}} \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta \end{bmatrix} (z + w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (z - w|2\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

$$+2 \sum_{\substack{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g \\ \epsilon \nu \text{ even}}} \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z + w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z - w|2\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Proof. By the definition of F we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & F(z|\Omega) F(w|\Omega) \\ &= \left(\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (w|\Omega) - \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (w|\Omega) \right) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \left(\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (w|\Omega) + \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (w|\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \right) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Applying [B.3](#) and [B.1](#) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & F(z|\Omega) F(w|\Omega) \\ &= \sum_{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g} (1 - e^{2\pi i \alpha \epsilon} e^{\pi i \nu \epsilon}) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta \end{bmatrix} (z + w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (z - w|2\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \sum_{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g} (1 + e^{\pi i \nu \epsilon}) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z + w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z - w|2\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2. On the right side of [2.4](#) we have a total of 2^g summands (in each of the two sums, $2^g/2$ each). This corresponds to Hirota's scalar case, see [[6](#), (2.7)].

Problem 3. Under what conditions does F^{-1} exist?

To get answers to this problem, we make the following two alternative assumptions:

$$\Re\Omega = 0 \quad \Im z = 0 \quad 2\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}^g \tag{2.5}$$

or

$$\Re\Omega = 0 \quad \Re z = 0 \quad 2\beta \in \mathbb{Z}^g \quad 2\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}^g \quad 2\alpha\beta \in \mathbb{Z} \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{Z}. \tag{2.6}$$

With these assumptions, we will definitely get real solutions from [1.1](#):

Proposition 4. *With [2.5](#) or [2.6](#) we get real entries for the matrix $F(z|\Omega)$ defined in [2.3](#).*

Proof. In the case of 2.5 we can shift the summation index n by $2a$. Moreover, in the case of 2.6 we can shift the argument z by 2β and by $2\beta + \epsilon$. If we consider B.2 then everything else is clear. $\square$

Proposition 5. *Let $\Re\Omega = 0$, $\Re z = 0$, $\beta = \vec{0}$, $2\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}^g$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then $\det F(z|\Omega) > 0$.*

Proof. Because of the prerequisites applies 2.6. Therefore, the entries of $F(z|\Omega)$ are real. It is also clear that $\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \vec{0} \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) > 0$. $\square$

Proposition 6. *Let $\Re\Omega = 0$, $\Im z = 0$, $\alpha = \vec{0}$. Then $\det F(z|\Omega) > 0$.*

Proof. The assertion follows from the POISSON sum formula, see B.5. $\square$

If $\Im z = 0$ and $\alpha \neq \vec{0}$, then we only have a result for $g = 2$:

Proposition 7. *Let $g = 2$, $\Re\Omega = 0$, $\Im z = 0$, $2\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}^2$. Furthermore, $\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \frac{1}{2}m \end{bmatrix} (0|\Omega) \neq 0$ or $\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \frac{1}{2}m + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (0|\Omega) \neq 0$ for $m = [0, 0], [1, 0], [1, 0], [1, 1]$. Then $\det F(z|\Omega) > 0$.*

Proof. There is no loss of generality in assuming $\beta = 0$, since β means only a real shift of the argument z . By Proposition 4. and 2.2 we have to show that $\theta(z + \Omega\alpha|\Omega)$ and $\theta(z + \Omega\alpha + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon|\Omega)$ have no common real zeros z . So far, because of B.6, we only know that there are two common incongruent zeros. We now show that these zeros can not be real. If z is a common zero, then it must also be $z + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon$. Both are incongruent. Therefore applies because of B.7 the identity $2z + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \equiv -2\Omega\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\epsilon$ and consequently $2z \equiv 0$. From the definition of “ $\equiv$ ” it follows that $z = \frac{1}{2}\Omega m_1 + \frac{1}{2}m_2$ for certain $m_1, m_2 \in \mathbb{Z}^2$. Suppose $m_1 \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2$, then the common zeros would not be real. So only the case remains $z = \frac{1}{2}m_2$. However, according to the precondition, the statement $\theta(\frac{1}{2}m_2 + \Omega\alpha|\Omega) \neq 0$ or $\theta(\frac{1}{2}m_2 + \Omega\alpha + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon|\Omega) \neq 0$ apply to all $m_2 \in \mathbb{Z}^2$. $\square$

Corollary 8. *Let $g = 2$, $\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{11} & \omega_{12} \\ \omega_{12} & \omega_{22} \end{bmatrix}$, $\Re\Omega = 0$, $\Im z = 0$, $2\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}^2$. Then $\det F(z|\Omega) > 0$ holds for sufficiently small $|\omega_{12}|$, if one of the three conditions is fulfilled:*

- (i) $\alpha = [0, 0]$
- (ii) $\alpha = \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right], \epsilon \neq [1, 0]$.
- (iii) $\alpha = \left[\frac{1}{2}, 0\right], \epsilon \neq [0, 1]$

($\epsilon = [0, 0]$ is by definition excluded.)

Proof. If $\omega_{12} = 0$ then $\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \beta_1 \end{bmatrix} (z_1|\omega_{11}) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_2 \\ \beta_2 \end{bmatrix} (z_2|\omega_{22})$. Here, $\alpha = [\alpha_1, \alpha_2]$ and $\alpha = [\beta_1, \beta_2]$. Moreover, the theta constants $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}$ and $\theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$ are different from zero, see [4, <https://dlmf.nist.gov/20.4.i>, <https://dlmf.nist.gov/21.2.iii>]. If (i) or (ii) or (iii) applies, then the prerequisites of Proposition 7 are satisfied. Since theta constants are continuous functions in Ω , the assertion is true. $\square$

3 Examples

3.1 Example 1

$g = 1 \quad \Re\omega = 0 \quad \Im z = 0 \quad \alpha = 1/2 \quad \epsilon = 1$ (cf. 2.5)

Then

$$F(z|\omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ \beta + 1/2 \end{bmatrix} (z|\omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

$$F(z|\omega) F(w|\omega)$$

=

$$2\theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ 2\beta \end{bmatrix} (z+w|2\omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (z-w|2\omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + 2\theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ 2\beta + 1/2 \end{bmatrix} (z+w|2\omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1/2 \end{bmatrix} (z-w|2\omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Remains to clarify whether the determinant

$$\det F(z|\omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ \beta \end{bmatrix}^2 (z|\omega) + \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ \beta + 1/2 \end{bmatrix}^2 (z|\omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^2 (z + \beta|\omega) + \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ 1/2 \end{bmatrix}^2 (z + \beta|\omega)$$

is not equal to zero. This is true, because of 2.5 the functions $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (z|\omega)$

and $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ 1/2 \end{bmatrix} (z|\omega)$ are real and have no common zeros, see [4, <https://dlmf.nist.gov/20.2.ii>].

Remark. Letting $\beta = \frac{1}{4}$ and taking

$$G(z|\omega) = -\frac{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}{2\hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}} F^2 \left(z/\pi\hat{\theta}^2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \middle| \omega \right)$$

gives

$$G(z|\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_c(2z|2\omega) & \theta_s(2z|2\omega) \\ -\theta_s(2z|2\omega) & \theta_c(2z|2\omega) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Here $\hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} = \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (0|2\Omega)$ denote *theta constants* for 2Ω and θ_s, θ_c the *Neville theta functions*, see [4, <https://dlmf.nist.gov/20.1>]. Furthermore

$$G^{-1}G_z = \frac{2}{\pi\hat{\theta}^2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} F^{-1}F' \left(z/\pi\hat{\theta}^2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right),$$

i.e. the result of the paper [1] as a special case of our considerations.

3.2 Example 2

$$g = 2 \quad \Omega = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{11} & \omega_{12} \\ \omega_{12} & \omega_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad \Re\Omega = 0 \quad z = [z_1, z_2] \quad \Im z = 0 \quad \alpha = [0, \frac{1}{2}] \quad \beta = [0, \frac{1}{2}] \quad \epsilon = [1, 1]$$

(c.f. 2.5)

Then

$$F(z|\Omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& F(z|\Omega) F(w|\Omega) \\
&= \\
&= 2 \left\{ \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z+w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z-w|2\Omega) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z+w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z-w|2\Omega) \right\} \\
&\quad \times \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
&+ \\
&2 \left\{ \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} (z+w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} (z-w|2\Omega) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} (z-w|2\Omega) \right\} \\
&\quad \times \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

We know from Proposition 7 that $\det F(z|\Omega) > 0$ if $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} (0|\Omega) \neq 0$.

Problem 9. For which twodimensional RIEMANN matrices Ω with $\Re\Omega = 0$, $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} (0|\Omega) \neq 0$? In particular, if $\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & \omega_{22} \end{bmatrix}$, then $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} (0|\Omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1/2 \end{bmatrix} (0|\omega_{11}) \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (0|\omega_{22}) \neq 0$. For reasons of continuity, this statement also applies to sufficiently small $|\omega_{12}|$.

3.3 Example 3

$g = 3$ $\Re\Omega = 0$ $\alpha = \beta = [0, 0, 0]$ $\epsilon = [0, 1, 1]$ (c.f. 2.6 and 2.5).

We abbreviate $\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|2\Omega)$ to $\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\alpha} \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z)$. Then

$$F(z|\Omega) F(w|\Omega)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 2 \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z-w) + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \hat{1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \hat{1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z-w) + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z-w) + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \hat{1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \hat{1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (z-w) \right) \times \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
&+ 2 \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z-w) + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z-w) + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z-w) + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z+w) \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \hat{1} \end{bmatrix} (z-w) \right) \times \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

4 Hirota-KdV equation for commuting matrices

Hirota in his famous work [5] shows that the double of the logarithmic derivative $V = 2F^{-1}F_x$ of a scalar function F is a scalar solution of the Hirota-KdV equation 1.1 with scalar C if F satisfies the bilinear differential equation

$$D_x (D_t + D_x^3) F \cdot F = C \cdot F \cdot F, \quad (4.1)$$

where the bilinear differential operators are defined by

$$D_x^n D_t^m F(x, t) \cdot G(x, t) = \left[\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \right)^m F(x, t) \cdot G(x', t') \right]_{x'=x, t'=t}. \quad (4.2)$$

Proposition 10. *Hirota's theorem remains valid if we assume that F , G and C are matrices of the form $\begin{bmatrix} f & h \\ -h & f \end{bmatrix}$.*

Proof. In this case C , F , G , F^{-1} , G^{-1} , F_x , G_x , F_{xt} , G_{xt} etc. commute with each other. $\square$

Lemma 11. *Let $F(u, v)$, $G(u, v)$ scalar or matrix valued functions. Then we have*

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left[\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \right)^m F(x+x', t+t') \cdot G(x-x', t-t') \right]_{x'=x, t'=t} \\
&= 2^{n+m} F(2x, 2t) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial u} \right)^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v} \right)^m G(u, v) \Big|_{u=0, v=0}.
\end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

Proof. From the product rule of differentiation it follows that

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) F(x+x') \cdot G(x-x') = 2F(x+x') \cdot G'(x-x').$$

Here G' denote the derivative of G . Repeated application of this formula yields the assertion. $\square$

Theorem 12. Let (i) $\alpha \cdot \epsilon \pmod{1} = 1/2$ or (ii) $\alpha \cdot \epsilon \pmod{1} = 0$. Furthermore, let $a, b \in \mathbb{C}^g$, $c \in \mathbb{C}$, $C = c \cdot I_g$ ($I_g = g \times g$ identity matrix) and Ω a Riemann matrix. Denote $\frac{\partial}{\partial e} = e_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial z_1} + e_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial z_2}$. If the conditions

$$\sum_{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g} \theta \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta \end{matrix} \right] (2ax + 2bt|2\Omega) \left[(4\partial_a \partial_b + 16\partial_a^4 - c) \theta \left[\begin{matrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 0 \end{matrix} \right] (z|2\Omega) \right]_{z=0} = 0$$

(i) $\epsilon\nu$ even
(ii) $\epsilon\nu$ odd

$$\sum_{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g} \theta \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{matrix} \right] (z + w|2\Omega) \left[(4\partial_a \partial_b + 16\partial_a^4 - c) \theta \left[\begin{matrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{matrix} \right] (z - w|2\Omega) \right]_{z=0} = 0$$

$\epsilon\nu$ even

(4.4)

applies to all x and t , then

$$F(ax + bt|\Omega) = \theta \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{matrix} \right] (ax + bt|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \theta \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha \\ \beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{matrix} \right] (ax + bt|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

is a solution of the bilinear differential equation 4.1.

Proof. Substituting $z = ax + bt$, $w = ax' + bt'$ into 2.4 yields

$$\begin{aligned}
& D_x (D_t + D_x^3) F(ax + bt) \cdot F(ax + bt) - C \cdot F(ax + bt) \cdot F(ax + bt) \\
&= \\
& \left[\left(\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^4 - c \right) F(ax + bt) \cdot F(ax' + bt') \right] \Big|_{x'=x, t'=t} \\
&= \\
& 2 \sum_{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g} \left(\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^4 - c \right) \left(\right. \\
& \quad (i) \ \epsilon \nu \text{ even} \\
& \quad (ii) \ \epsilon \nu \text{ odd} \\
& \left. \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta \end{bmatrix} (a(x + x') + b(t + t') | 2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (a(x - x') + b(t - t') | 2\Omega) \right) \Big|_{x'=x, t'=t} \\
& \times \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
& + \\
& 2 \sum_{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g} \left(\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^4 - c \right) \left(\right. \\
& \quad \epsilon \nu \text{ even} \\
& \left. \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 2\beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (a(x + x') + b(t + t') | 2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (a(x - x') + b(t - t') | 2\Omega) \right) \Big|_{x'=x, t'=t} \\
& \times \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned}$$

and applying Lemma 11. then gives the assertion. $\square$

Corollary 13. *Let (i) $\alpha \cdot \epsilon \pmod{1} = 1/2$ or (ii) $\alpha \cdot \epsilon \pmod{1} = 0$. Furthermore, let $a, b \in \mathbb{C}^g$, $c \in \mathbb{C}$, $C = c \cdot I_g$ ($I_g = g \times g$ identity matrix) and Ω a Riemann matrix. Denote $\frac{\partial}{\partial e} = e_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial z_1} + e_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial z_2}$. If the conditions*

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[(4 \partial_a \partial_b + 16 \partial_a^4 - c) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (z | 2\Omega) \right]_{z=0} = 0 \\
& \text{for all } \nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g \text{ with } \epsilon \nu \text{ even if (i) or } \epsilon \nu \text{ odd if (ii) and}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[(4 \partial_a \partial_b + 16 \partial_a^4 - c) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\nu \\ \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (z | 2\Omega) \right]_{z=0} = 0 \\
& \text{for all } \nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g \text{ with } \epsilon \nu \text{ even}
\end{aligned}$$

applies to all x and t , then

$$F(ax + bt | \Omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (ax + bt | \Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon \end{bmatrix} (ax + bt | \Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

is a solution of the bilinear differential equation 4.1. In addition, $\det F(ax + bt|\Omega) \neq 0$ for all x and t , then $V = 2F^{-1}F_x$ is a (complex) solution of the Hirota-KdV equation 1.1.

5 Examples: continuation

5.1 Example 1

Example 1 (3.1) leads to the following result:

Proposition 14. *Let $g = 1$, $\Re\omega = 0$, $\Im z = 0$, $\alpha = 1/2$, $\epsilon = 1$. Furthermore, let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, $c \in \mathbb{R}$, $C = c \cdot I_2$. If for every characteristics E of*

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

the condition

$$[(4\partial_a\partial_b + 16\partial_a^4 - c)\theta[E](z|\Omega)]_{z=0} = 0 \quad (5.1)$$

is true then

$$F(z|\omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 \\ \beta + 1/2 \end{bmatrix} (z|\omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

is a solution of the bilinear differential equation 4.1. In addition $V = 2F^{-1}F_x$ is a real solution of the Hirota-KdV equation 1.1:

$$V_t + 3V_xV_x + V_{xxx} = C.$$

For given values of a and ω , the conditions 5.1 represent a linear system of equations for the unknowns b and c :

$$\begin{aligned} 4a\hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} b - \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} c &= -16a^4\hat{\theta}'''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ 4a\hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} b - \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} c &= -16a^4\hat{\theta}'''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Here $\hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} = \frac{d^2}{dz^2}\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|2\Omega)|_{z=0}$ etc.. We compute the unknowns b and

c by means of Cramer's rule:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= -4a \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \end{vmatrix} \\ b &= \frac{16a^4}{\Delta} \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\theta}''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \end{vmatrix} \\ c &= \frac{-64a^5}{\Delta} \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta}''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \end{vmatrix}\end{aligned}$$

We calculate these three determinants with the addition formula [B.3](#) by putting the left side equal to $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} (z|\omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} (w|\omega)$, $z = \frac{u+v}{2}$, $w = \frac{u-v}{2}$ and forming the differentials $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial v^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial u^2}$, $\frac{\partial^4}{\partial v^4} - \frac{\partial^4}{\partial u^4}$, $\frac{\partial^6}{\partial z^5 \partial w}$ of the equation in the place $u = v = 0$ successively. We obtain

$$\begin{aligned}-\theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}^2 &= \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \end{vmatrix} \\ -\theta''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} \theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\theta}''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \\ \hat{\theta}''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \end{vmatrix} \\ -\frac{1}{8} \left(\theta'''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} \theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} - \theta''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} \theta''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} \right) &= \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta}''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \\ \hat{\theta}'' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} & \hat{\theta}''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \end{vmatrix} \quad (5.2)\end{aligned}$$

It is easy to check that $\theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} \neq 0$. Thus we have $b = -4a^3 \frac{\theta''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}}{\theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}}$ and

$$c = -2a^4 \left(\frac{\theta'''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}}{\theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}} - \left(\frac{\theta''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}}{\theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}} \right)^2 \right)$$

5.2 Example 2

Example 2 (3.2) leads to the following result:

Proposition 15. *Let $g = 2$, $\Re\Omega = 0$, $\alpha = [0, \frac{1}{2}]$, $\beta = [0, \frac{1}{2}]$, $\epsilon = [1, 1]$. Furthermore, let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $c \in \mathbb{R}$, $C = c \cdot I_2$. If $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (0|\Omega) \neq 0$ and for every characteristics E of (the Göpel group)*

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

the condition

$$[(4\partial_a\partial_b + 16\partial_a^4 - c)\theta[E](z|\Omega)]_{z=0} = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

is true, then

$$F(ax + bt|\Omega) = \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} (ax + bt|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} (ax + bt|\Omega) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

is a solution of the bilinear differential equation 4.1. In addition $V = 2F^{-1}F_x$ is a real solution of the Hirota-KdV equation 1.1:

$$V_t + 3V_xV_x + V_{xxx} = C.$$

For given values of a and Ω , the conditions 5.3 represent a linear system of equations for the unknowns b_1 , b_2 and c . To see this, let

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad D = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then, with the abbreviations

$$E_{ij} = \partial_{z_1}^i \partial_{z_2}^j \theta[E](z|\Omega)|_{z=0} \quad E = A, B, C, D,$$

this system of equations assumes the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
4(a_1A_{20} + a_2A_{11})b_1 + 4(a_1A_{11} + a_2A_{02})b_2 - cA_{00} &= rhs_1 \\
4(a_1B_{20} + a_2B_{11})b_1 + 4(a_1B_{11} + a_2B_{02})b_2 - cB_{00} &= rhs_2 \\
4(a_1C_{20} + a_2C_{11})b_1 + 4(a_1C_{11} + a_2C_{02})b_2 - cC_{00} &= rhs_3 \\
4(a_1D_{20} + a_2D_{11})b_1 + 4(a_1D_{11} + a_2D_{02})b_2 - cD_{00} &= rhs_4
\end{aligned} \tag{5.4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
rhs_1 &= -16(a_1^4A_{40} + 4a_1^3a_2A_{31} + 6a_1^2a_2^2A_{22} + 4a_1a_2^3A_{13} + a_2^4A_{04}) \\
rhs_2 &= -16(a_1^4B_{40} + 4a_1^3a_2B_{31} + 6a_1^2a_2^2B_{22} + 4a_1a_2^3B_{13} + a_2^4B_{04}) \\
rhs_3 &= -16(a_1^4C_{40} + 4a_1^3a_2C_{31} + 6a_1^2a_2^2C_{22} + 4a_1a_2^3C_{13} + a_2^4C_{04}) \\
rhs_4 &= -16(a_1^4D_{40} + 4a_1^3a_2D_{31} + 6a_1^2a_2^2D_{22} + 4a_1a_2^3D_{13} + a_2^4D_{04}).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have an overdetermined equation system with 3 unknowns and 4 equations. The singularity of the extended coefficient matrix provides a necessary condition for the solution of this system:

$$\begin{vmatrix} A_{20} & A_{11} & A_{00} & A_{40} \\ B_{20} & B_{11} & B_{00} & B_{40} \\ C_{20} & C_{11} & C_{00} & C_{40} \\ D_{20} & D_{11} & D_{00} & D_{40} \end{vmatrix} \times q^6 + (\dots) \times q^5 + \dots - \begin{vmatrix} A_{02} & A_{11} & A_{00} & A_{04} \\ B_{02} & B_{11} & B_{00} & B_{04} \\ C_{02} & C_{11} & C_{00} & C_{04} \\ D_{02} & D_{11} & D_{00} & D_{04} \end{vmatrix} = 0 \tag{5.5}$$

with

$$q = \frac{a_1}{a_2}.$$

To construct real solutions of 1.1, we need real zeros q . For example, this is correct for $\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} \omega & \omega' \\ \omega' & \omega \end{bmatrix}$.

Clearly, if q is a zero of 5.5 and b'_1, b'_2, c' represent a solution of 5.4 for $a_2 = 1$ and $a_1 = q$, then $b_1 = a_2^3b'_1, b_2 = a_2^3b'_2, c = a_2^4c'$ represent a solution of 5.4 for $a_1 = a_2q$, where a_2 is arbitrary.

6 Examples: numerical results

6.1 Example 1

Let (5.2):

$$b = a^3 b' \quad b' = -4 \frac{\theta''' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} (0|\omega)}{\theta' \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} (0|\omega)}.$$

Then we see that b' changes the sign, so it can become 0, see A.3:

6.2 Example 2

Remark 16. The following numerical examples have been created by trial and error: a module Ω was searched, so that $\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (0|\Omega) \neq 0$ and for given a the system 5.4 has a unique solution b_1, b_2, c .

6.2.1 Under example 2.1

Consider Example 2 (3.2) with $\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} 0.525 & 0.225 \\ 0.225 & 0.45 \end{bmatrix} i$. Then

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \left([0, 0] \mid \begin{bmatrix} 0.525 & 0.225 \\ 0.225 & 0.45 \end{bmatrix} i \right) = 0.687222586858098 \neq 0,$$

cf. A.1. Because of Proposition 7, $\det F(z|\Omega) \neq 0$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The determinant of the extended coefficient matrix (5.5) now looks like this:

$$\begin{aligned} & -2132766.706014718q^6 + 109736.9805502547q^5 + 7957661.595856786q^4 \\ & \quad -1032263.1256386703q^3 - 8942035.54821402q^2 \\ & \quad + 1405541.2010413697q + 2631917.500875636 \end{aligned}$$

cf. A.4 and the q 's for which the extended coefficient matrix is singular are:

$$\begin{aligned} q_1 &= 0.9783104837639065 \\ q_2 &= -0.5481200386182866 \\ q_3 &= -1.31098301812922 \\ q_4 &= 1.021175138726851 \\ q_5 &= 1.267400395011165 \\ q_6 &= -1.356330084900353 \end{aligned}$$

For each of these six q 's we get exactly one (numerical) solution b'_1 , b'_2 , c' . For example, $q_5 = 1.267400395011165$ we get $b'_1 = 229.387880221197$, $b'_2 = 229.380482031660$ and $c' = 136.591582550493$. In this case, our argument in ansatz 3.2 takes the form:

$$z = [1, 1.267400395011165]a_2x + [229.387880221197, 229.380482031660]a_2^3t,$$

where a_2 is arbitrary real. Graphically, it looks like this ($a = 0.5$):

6.2.2 Under example 2.2

Consider under example 2.1. If we choose $q_3 = -1.31098301812924$, we get $b'_1 = -17.2921249803303$, $b'_2 = -12.2920900448762$ and $c' = 48836.5992934489$. In this case, our argument in ansatz 3.2 takes the form:

$$z = [1, -1.31098301812924]a_2x + [-17.2921249803303, -12.2920900448762]a_2^3t,$$

where a_2 is arbitrary real. Graphically, it looks like this ($a = 0.5$):

6.2.3 Under example 2.3

Consider Example 2 (3.2) with $\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} 0.13125 & 0.05625 \\ 0.05625 & 0.1125 \end{bmatrix} i$. Then:

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \left([0, 0] \mid \begin{bmatrix} 0.13125 & 0.05625 \\ 0.05625 & 0.1125 \end{bmatrix} i \right) = 0.00914518791715402 \neq 0,$$

cf. A.1. Because of Proposition 7, $\det F(z|\Omega) \neq 0$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}^2$. For $q = 0.200294149789154$ we get $b'_1 = 627.595407829435$, $b'_2 = -251.944426411163$ and $c' = 100790.103767288$. In this case, our argument in ansatz 3.2 takes the form:

$$z = [1, 0.200294149789154]a_2x + [627.595407829435, -251.944426411163]a_2^3t,$$

where a_2 is arbitrary real. Graphically, it looks like this ($a = 0.25$):

6.2.4 Under example 2.4

Consider Example 2 (3.2) with $\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} 2.1 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1.0 \end{bmatrix} i$. Then

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \left([0, 0] \mid \begin{bmatrix} 2.1 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1.0 \end{bmatrix} i \right) = 0.881256803554296 \neq 0,$$

Because of Proposition 7, $\det F(z|\Omega) \neq 0$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The q 's for which the extended coefficient matrix is singular are:

$$\begin{aligned} q_1 &= 0.391426753221707 \\ q_2 &= 0.9999809616004972 \\ q_3 &= 1.000019087438852 \\ q_4 &= -5.557886777744076 \\ q_5 &= 43.4916140704104 \\ q_6 &= -45.0812250080816 \end{aligned}$$

For each of these six q 's we get one (numerical) solution b'_1, b'_2, c' . If we choose $q_4 = -5.557886777744076$, we get $b'_1 = -10900.3245374826$, $b'_2 = 157.850201871195$ and $c' = 19649.2732401678$. In this case, our argument in ansatz 3.2 takes the form:

$$z = [1, -5.557886777744076]a_2x + [-10900.3245374826, 157.850201871195]a_2^3t,$$

where a_2 is arbitrary real. Graphically, it looks like this ($a = 0.5$):

6.2.5 Under example 2.5

Consider under example 2.4. If we choose $q_6 = -45.0812250080816$, we get $b'_1 = -3.60525766877222 \times 10^6$, $b'_2 = 231494.478506133$ and $c' = 4.79056679648272 \times 10^7$. In this case, our argument in ansatz 3.2 takes the form:

$$z = [1, -45.0812250080816]a_2x + [-3.60525766877222 \times 10^6, 231494.478506133]a_2^3t,$$

where a_2 is arbitrary real. Graphically, it looks like this ($a = 0.5$):

6.3 Example 3

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A Examples: sage code

A.1 RiemannTheta function from *Abelfunctions*

Abelfunctions is a SAGEMATH library from C. Swierczewski et al. for computing with *Abelian functions*, cf. [11, 12]. For example, to get

$$\theta\left([0,0] \mid \begin{bmatrix} 2.1 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1.8 \end{bmatrix} i\right) = 1.01245688872$$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial z_1^3 \partial z_2} \theta\left(z \mid \begin{bmatrix} 2.1 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1.8 \end{bmatrix} i\right) \Big|_{z=[0,0]} = -4.25174278845,$$

do the following:

```

1 sage: from abelfunctions import RiemannTheta
2 sage: Omega=matrix(CDF,[[2.1*I,0.9*I],[0.9*I,1.8*I]])
3 sage: z=[0,0]
4 sage: print(RiemannTheta(z,Omega))
5 sage: print(RiemannTheta(z,Omega, derivs=[[1,0],[1,0],[1,0],[0,1]]))
6 (1.01245688872+0j)
7 (-4.25174278845+0j)

```

A.2 Theta function with characteristics

In this section we give an implementation of the theta function with characteristics based on the RiemannTheta function from *Abelfunctions*. We use the formula <https://dlmf.nist.gov/21.2.E6> and the LEIBNIZ rule. We need four auxiliary functions:

```

1 sage: def make_index_list(diff): # index list for Leibniz's rule
2 ...     index_list=[] #return value
3 ...     g=len(diff)
4 ...     if g==1:
5 ...         index_list=[[i] for i in range(diff[0]+1)]
6 ...     if g > 1:
7 ...         l=[]
8 ...         for d in diff:
9 ...             l.append(range(d+1))
10 ...         index_list=cartesian_product(l).list()
11 ...     return index_list

```

```

1 sage: def make_derivs(diff):
2 ...     derivs=[]
3 ...     g=len(diff)
4 ...     E=identity_matrix(g)
5 ...     for i in range(g):
6 ...         if diff[i]>0:
7 ...             for k in range(diff[i]):
8 ...                 derivs.append(list(E[i]))
9 ...     return derivs

1 sage: def binom(diff ,index):
2 ...     prod=1 #return value
3 ...     g=len(diff)
4 ...     if g > 0:
5 ...         for i in range(g):
6 ...             if index[i] > 0: prod=prod*binomial(diff[i],index[i])
7 ...     return prod

1 sage: def intern_deriv_exp(diff ,index , alpha ):
2 ...     fac=1 #return value
3 ...     l=len(index)
4 ...     for i in range(l):
5 ...         if diff[i] > index[i] : fac=fac*(2*pi*I*alpha[i])** (diff[i]-index[i])
6 ...     return fac

1 sage: def Theta(arg ,Modul ,Char=[], diff=[]):
2 ...     z=vector(arg)
3 ...     Omega=Modul
4 ...     r=0 # return value
5 ...     if Char==[]:
6 ...         if diff==[]: r=n(RiemannTheta(z,Omega))
7 ...         else: r=n(RiemannTheta(z,Omega,derivs=make_derivs(diff)))
8 ...     else:
9 ...         alpha=Char[0]
10 ...         beta=Char[1]
11 ...     if diff==[]: r=n(exp(I*pi*alpha*Omega*alpha+2*pi*I*alpha*(z+beta))*\
12 ...         RiemannTheta(z+Omega*alpha+beta ,Modul))
13 ...     else:
14 ...         index_list=make_index_list(diff)
15 ...         for index in index_list:
16 ...             r=r+RiemannTheta(z+Omega*alpha+beta ,Modul,derivs=make_derivs(index))*\
17 ...             binom(diff ,index)*intern_deriv_exp(diff ,index ,alpha)
18 ...         r=r*exp(I*pi*alpha*Omega*alpha+2*pi*I*alpha*(z+beta))
19 ...     return n(r)

```

For example, to get

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \left([0,0] \mid \begin{bmatrix} 2.1 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1.8 \end{bmatrix} i \right) = 0.475187316670386 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial z_1^3 \partial z_2} \theta \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \left(z \mid \begin{bmatrix} 2.1 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1.8 \end{bmatrix} i \right) \Big|_{z=[0,0]} = 8.80091339461615, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

do the following:

```

1 sage: E=matrix ([[0 ,0.5] , [0.5 ,0]])
2 sage: Omega=matrix (CDF, [[2.1*I ,0.9*I] , [0.9*I ,1.8*I]])
3 sage: w=[0 ,0]
4 sage: print (Theta (w, Omega, Char=E))
5 0.475187316670386 + 1.81398063786072e-35*I
6 sage: print (Theta (w, Omega, Char=E, diff = [3 ,1]))
7 8.80091339461615 + 5.75641808698091e-31*I

```

A.3 Example 1

```

1 sage: def bline (omega):
2 ...     r=real_part (Theta ([0] , matrix ([[ omega*I ]]) , \
3 ...     Char=G, diff = [3]) / theta ([0] , matrix ([[ omega*I ]]) , Char=G, diff = [1]))
4 ...     return -4*r
5 sage: plot (lambda omega: bline (omega) , (0.1 , 0.5) , axes_labels = [ '$\Im\omega$' , '$b\ '$' ])

```

A.4 Example 2

Extended coefficient matrix (5.5):

```

1 sage: A=matrix ([[0 ,0] , [0 ,0]]) ; B=matrix ([[0.5 ,0.5] , [0 ,0]]) ;
2 sage: C=matrix ([[0 ,0] , [0.5 ,0.5]]) ; D=matrix ([[0.5 ,0.5] , [0.5 ,0.5]])
3 sage: A00=Theta (w, 2*Omega, Char=A, diff = [0 ,0]) ; A20=Theta (w, 2*Omega, Char=A, diff = [2 ,0]) ;
4 ...     ...
5 sage: D13=real_part (Theta (w, 2*Omega, Char=D, diff = [1 ,3])) ;
6 sage: D04=real_part (Theta (w, 2*Omega, Char=D, diff = [0 ,4]))
7 sage: q=var ('q' , domain='real ')
8 sage: ext_coeff_matrix=matrix ([[
9 [4*(q*A20+A11) , 4*(q*A11+A02) , -A00 , -16*(q**4*A40+4*q**3*A31+6*q**2*A22+4*q*A13+A04)] , \
10 [4*(q*B20+B11) , 4*(q*B11+B02) , -B00 , -16*(q**4*B40+4*q**3*B31+6*q**2*B22+4*q*B13+B04)] , \
11 [4*(q*C20+C11) , 4*(q*C11+C02) , -C00 , -16*(q**4*C40+4*q**3*C31+6*q**2*C22+4*q*C13+C04)] , \
12 [4*(q*D20+D11) , 4*(q*D11+D02) , -D00 , -16*(q**4*D40+4*q**3*D31+6*q**2*D22+4*q*D13+D04)]])

```

The determinant of the extended coefficient matrix (5.5):

```

1 sage: det=ext_coeff_matrix.det (); det

```

All q 's for which the extended coefficient matrix is singular:

```

1 sage: det_maxima=maxima (repr (det))
2 sage: roots=det_maxima.allroots ()
3 sage: repr (roots)

```

Selection of a q :

```

1 sage: q=sage_eval (repr (roots [4]. rhs ()))
2 sage: m=ext_coeff_matrix.substitute (q=q)

```

Singularity of m :

```

1 sage: m.det ()

```

Calculation of b'_1 , b'_2 and c' :

```

1 sage: n=m.delete_rows([3])
2 sage: n_rref=n.rref();n_rref
3 sage: b1line=n_rref[0,3]; b2line=n_rref[1,3]; cline=n_rref[2,3]; b1line; b2line; cline
4 sage: print(m.delete_columns([3])*((n_rref).column(3))) # test if solution

```

The following three functions serve to compute $U(x, t) = V_x(x, t) = V_x^0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} +$

$$V_x^1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}:$$

```

1 def detF(v, diff=[]):
2     r=0
3     a=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E))
4     b=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G))
5     if diff==[]:
6         r=a**2+b**2
7     else:
8         if diff==[1,0] or diff==[0,1]:
9             a1=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=diff))
10            b1=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=diff))
11            r=2*(a*a1+b*b1)
12        if diff==[1,1]:
13            a10=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[1,0]))
14            b10=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[1,0]))
15            a01=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[0,1]))
16            b01=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[0,1]))
17            a11=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[1,1]))
18            b11=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[1,1]))
19            r=2*(a10*a01+a*a11+b10*b01+b*b11)
20        if diff==[2,0]:
21            a10=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[1,0]))
22            b10=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[1,0]))
23            a20=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[2,0]))
24            b20=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[2,0]))
25            r=2*(a10*a10+a*a20+b10*b10+b*b20)
26        if diff==[0,2]:
27            a01=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[0,1]))
28            b01=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[0,1]))
29            a02=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[0,2]))
30            b02=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[0,2]))
31            r=2*(a01*a01+a*a02+b01*b01+b*b02)
32    return r

1 def V0_x(x, t):
2     f00=detF([a*x+a**3*b1line*t, a*q*x+a**3*b2line*t])
3     f10=detF([a*x+a**3*b1line*t, a*q*x+a**3*b2line*t], diff=[1,0])
4     f01=detF([a*x+a**3*b1line*t, a*q*x+a**3*b2line*t], diff=[0,1])
5     f20=detF([a*x+a**3*b1line*t, a*q*x+a**3*b2line*t], diff=[2,0])
6     f11=detF([a*x+a**3*b1line*t, a*q*x+a**3*b2line*t], diff=[1,1])
7     f02=detF([a*x+a**3*b1line*t, a*q*x+a**3*b2line*t], diff=[0,2])
8     r=(a**2*f20+2*a**2*q*f11+a**2*q**2*f02-(a*f10+a*q*f01)**2/f00)/f00
9     return r

1 def V1_x(x, t):
2     v=[a*x+a**3*b1line*t, a*q*x+a**3*b2line*t]

```

```

3      f00=detF(v)
4      a00=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E))
5      b00=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G))
6      a10=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[1,0]))
7      b10=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[1,0]))
8      a01=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[0,1]))
9      b01=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[0,1]))
10     a11=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[1,1]))
11     b11=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[1,1]))
12     a20=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[2,0]))
13     b20=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[2,0]))
14     a02=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=E, diff=[0,2]))
15     b02=real_part(Theta(v, Omega, Char=G, diff=[0,2]))
16     r=2*(a00*(a**2*b20+2*a*a*q*b11+a*q*a*q*b02)-b00*\
17         (a**2*a20+2*a*a*q*a11+a*q*a*q*a02))/f00-4*((a00*(a*b10+a*q*b01)-\
18         (a*a10+a*q*a01)*b00)*(a00*(a*a10+a*q*a01)+b00*(a*b10+a*q*b01))\
19         /f00**2
20     return r

```

For example, to get graphs of V_x^0 and V_x^1 , do the following:

```

1 sage: Omega=matrix(CDF,[[2.1*I,0.9*I],[0.9*I,1.8*I]])
2 sage: E=matrix([[0,0.5],[0.5,0]]);G=matrix([[0,0.5],[0,0.5]])
3 sage: q=1.60246356357733; b1line=352.097802557338; b2line=343.748753326305; a=0.5

1 sage: Qmin1=plot(lambda x:V1_x(x,-0.02), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='green',\
2     legend_label='$y=V^1_x(x,-0.02)$')
3 sage: Q0=plot(lambda x: V1_x(x,0), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='green',\
4     legend_label='$y=V^1_x(x,0)$')
5 sage: Q1=plot(lambda x: V1_x(x,0.02), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='green',\
6     legend_label='$y=V^1_x(x,0.02)$')
7 sage: Q2=plot(lambda x: V1_x(x,0.04), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='green',\
8     legend_label='$y=V^1_x(x,0.04)$')
9 sage: Q3=plot(lambda x: V1_x(x,0.06), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='green',\
10    legend_label='$y=V^1_x(x,0.06)$')
11 sage: Q4=plot(lambda x: V1_x(x,0.08), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='green',\
12    legend_label='$y=V^1_x(x,0.08)$')
13 sage: Q5=plot(lambda x: V1_x(x,0.1), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='green',\
14    legend_label='$y=V^1_x(x,0.1)$')

1 sage: Pmin1=plot(lambda x:4*V0_x(x,-0.02), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='red',\
2     legend_label='$y=4V^0_x(x,-0.02)$')
3 sage: P0=plot(lambda x: 4*V0_x(x,0), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='red',\
4     legend_label='$y=4V^0_x(x,0)$')
5 sage: P1=plot(lambda x: 4*V0_x(x,0.02), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='red',\
6     legend_label='$y=4V^0_x(x,0.02)$')
7 sage: P2=plot(lambda x: 4*V0_x(x,0.04), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='red',\
8     legend_label='$y=4V^0_x(x,0.04)$')
9 sage: P3=plot(lambda x: 4*V0_x(x,0.06), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='red',\
10    legend_label='$y=4V^0_x(x,0.06)$')
11 sage: P4=plot(lambda x: 4*V0_x(x,0.08), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='red',\
12    legend_label='$y=4V^0_x(x,0.08)$')
13 sage: P5=plot(lambda x: 4*V0_x(x,0.1), (0,4), axes_labels=['x$', '$y$'], color='red',\
14    legend_label='$y=4V^0_x(x,0.1)$')

1 (Pmin1+Qmin1).save(tmp_filename()+'.svg')
2 (P0+Q0).save(tmp_filename()+'.svg')

```

```

3 (P1+Q1).save(tmp_filename()+'.svg')
4 (P2+Q2).save(tmp_filename()+'.svg')
5 (P3+Q3).save(tmp_filename()+'.svg')
6 (P4+Q4).save(tmp_filename()+'.svg')
7 (P5+Q5).save(tmp_filename()+'.svg')

1 (Pmin1+Qmin1).show()
2 (P0+Q0).show()
3 (P1+Q1).show()
4 (P2+Q2).show()
5 (P3+Q3).show()
6 (P4+Q4).show()
7 (P5+Q5).show()

1 sage: x,t=var('x,t')
2 sage: %time; c=contour_plot(lambda x,t:V1_x(x,t),(x,0,4),(t,-0.02,0.1),colorbar=True,\
3 labels=False,axes_labels=['$x$', '$t$'],fill=True,aspect_ratio=20, title='$V^1_x(x,t)$')

```

A.5 Example 3

B Material on multidimensional theta functions

With $m_1, m_2 \in \mathbb{Z}^g$

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + m_1 \\ \beta + m_2 \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) = e^{2\pi i \alpha \cdot m_2} \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

see [4, <http://dlmf.nist.gov/21.3.E4>]. From this, it follows that the elements of α and β are usually restricted to $[0, 1)$, without loss of generality. Characteristics whose elements are either 0 or $\frac{1}{2}$ are known as *half-period characteristics*. Moreover,

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z + m_1 + m_2 \Omega|\Omega) = e^{2\pi i (\alpha m_1 - \beta m_2 - \frac{1}{2} m_2 \Omega m_2 - m_2 z)} \theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega), \quad (\text{B.2})$$

see [4, <http://dlmf.nist.gov/21.3.E5>]. Consequently, it suffices to consider the zeros of $\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega)$ in the parallelotope $z = \Omega \mu_1 + \mu_2$ whereby the elements of the g -dimensional real vectors μ_1 and μ_2 are restricted to $[0, 1)$. We call two points in $z_1, z_2 \in \mathbb{C}^g$ *congruent* ($z_1 \equiv z_2$), if they differ by $\Omega m_1 + m_2$ for certain $m_1, m_2 \in \mathbb{Z}^g$.

Furthermore, we will need the *addition formula*

$$\theta \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} (z|\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ \delta \end{bmatrix} (w|\Omega) = \sum_{\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^g / 2\mathbb{Z}^g} \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}[\alpha + \beta + \nu] \\ \gamma + \delta \end{bmatrix} (z + w|2\Omega) \theta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}[\alpha - \beta + \nu] \\ \gamma - \delta \end{bmatrix} (z - w|2\Omega) \quad (\text{B.3})$$

with $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{R}^g$, see [4, <http://dlmf.nist.gov/21.6.E8>]. Thus ν is a g -dimensional vector whose entries are either 0 or 1.

Furthermore, applies

$$\theta(z|\Omega) = \frac{\exp(-\pi iz\Omega^{-1}z)}{\sqrt{\det(-i\Omega)}} \theta(\Omega^{-1}z | -\Omega^{-1}), \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where the square root assumes its principal value, cf. [4, <https://dlmf.nist.gov/21.5.E8>]. From this follows POISSON *sum formula*, cf. e.g. [3, 7.10.]

$$\theta(z|\Omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\det(-i\Omega)}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^g} e^{-\pi i(n+z)\Omega^{-1}(n+z)}. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

For $g \geq 2$ let $c^1, \dots, c^g$ constant g -dimensional complex vectors that are incongruent in pairs. Then the equation system

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(z - c^1|\Omega) &= 0 \\ \theta(z - c^2|\Omega) &= 0 \\ \dots &= 0 \\ \theta(z - c^g|\Omega) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

has $g!$ incongruent solutions z , see [8, I.4. XI. Satz]. In addition, the formula

$$\sum z \equiv (g-1)! \sum_{i=1}^g c^i \quad (\text{B.7})$$

applies, see [8, I.4. (92)].

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